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Exchange Rate Fluctuations And Economic Growth In Nigeria

¹Henry Obukohwo OBEH PhD & ²Bright Onoriode OHWOFASA PhD

^{1,2}Department of Social Science (Economics Unit),
School of General Studies

Delta State Polytechnics, Otefe-Oghara, Nigeria

¹obehobus@gmail.com; +2348038351314

²brightohwofasa@Ogharapoly.edu.ng; +2348036793389

ABSTRACT

The effect of fluctuations in exchange rate has tended to undermine the growth performance of emerging economies such as Nigeria in which the extent of deterioration has generated heated debates in the extant literature that has necessitated copious empirical studies. Despite the high volume of literature aimed at profiling solutions, the problems continue to linger. Therefore, the study assessed the impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data for the period, 2000-2022. The real gross domestic product used as proxy for economic growth was made as the dependent variable while exchange rate, inflation rate and foreign reserves were the independent variables. The OLS technique was employed for the analysis. Accordingly, the study found that the exchange rate had significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Also, foreign reserves exerted positive and significant effect on economic growth. However, the impact of inflation rate on economic growth is negative but statistically insignificant. Therefore, the study recommended that effective policy based on fiscal and monetary tools should be made so as to achieve a realistic exchange rate for the naira. Finally, government may stir up efforts aimed at boosting productions thereby increasing output, exports and foreign reserves.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Foreign Exchange Rate, OLS, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The collapse of the Bretton Woods agreement in 1970 witnessed fundamental changes in the regime of the exchange rate across the global economies. A key noticeable feature is perhaps increasing use of floating exchange rates combined with flexible intermediate regimes including conventional pegs by most countries (Morina, *et al.*, 2020). This is predicated on the fear by many countries not to allow their nominal exchange rate to freely float at the international money market (Adewale, *et al.*, 2024). Essentially, the onus of maintaining stable exchange rate fixed by buying and selling currencies for the purpose of correcting the demand and supply of money rest on the central bank in countries where the fixed exchange rate is adopted. Some people have expressed disappointment on the difficulty of maintaining fixed exchange rate regime but rather submitted that investment and international trade are boosted and growth enhanced when nations attempt to keep a stable exchange rate along with macroeconomic stability (Ramon-Perazzi & Romero, 2022; Nwikina & Ekere, 2024). In 1973, floating exchange rates accounted for nominal and real interest rate volatility in Europe occasioned by risks associated with exchange rate and this further hampered the growth of investment. It is for this reason that

some economists believed that the growth of the economy may be hampered by floating exchange rates as most countries use the currency as an intermediate for the purchase of goods and services at the global market. As such volatility arising from the exchange rate made the countries concerned to face uncertainty in any agreement with other countries (Aslam, 2016; Morina, *et al.*, 2020).

It must be emphasized therefore that the primary purpose of government especially in developing country is to achieve the basic macroeconomic objectives which includes price stability, balance of payments equilibrium, high economic growth rate and exchange rate stability. Of the four macroeconomic objectives, exchange rate stability is relatively more pronounced. In many countries around the world including Nigeria, exchange rate floating was the usual practice, an arrangement which undergone significant changes in Nigeria over the last four decades. In the 1960s, a fixed regime arrangement was practiced while from 1970 till the mid 1980s the government practiced pegged exchange rate arrangement (Abdu, *et al.*, 2021). In 1979, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) applied the basket of currencies approach as a guide in the determination of the exchange rate using the relative strength of the currencies of the country's trading partner and the volume of trade with such countries. Specifically, appropriate weights were attached to such countries such as the United States of American dollars and the British Pounds Sterling on the exchange rate mechanism. In the conduct of foreign exchange management by government, economic consideration is usually the main focus in determining the exchange rate control. For instance, between, 1982-1984, the Nigerian currency was pegged to the British pound sterling on a 1.1 ratio. Prior to this time, the Naira has been devalued by 10% (Ehigiator, *et al.*, 2020; Adama, *et al.*, 2022).

Following the adoption of the structural adjustment programme (SAP) introduced by International Monetary Fund (IMF) in 1986, one of the key feature was to establish a realistic and sustainable exchange rate for the naira using the instrument of free market determined naira exchange rate through an auction system. According to Ewubare and Ushie (2022), SAP which is a regime of managed float without any strong commitment became the predominant characteristics of the floating regime in Nigeria. The fixed exchange rate regime induced an overvaluation of the naira and was supported by exchange rate control regulations that engendered significant distortions in the economy (Adeniran, *et al.*, 2014). This gave rise to massive importation of finished goods with adverse consequences for domestic production, balance of payments position and the level of external reserves (Akinwunmi & Adekoya, 2016). Likewise, the period was bedeviled by sharp practices perpetrated by dealers and end users of foreign exchange. The floating exchange rate regime implies that the forces of demand and supply determined the exchange rate. This regime assumed the absence of any visible hand in the foreign exchange market and that the exchange rate adjusts automatically to clear any deficit in the currency supply and demand in the market. This arrangement allowed the exchange rate to serve as a "buffer" for external shocks thereby permitting the monetary authorities full discretion in the conduct of monetary policy. This therefore marked the beginning of exchange rate fluctuations in Nigeria and the government had to establish the foreign exchange market (FEM) to stabilize the exchange rate depending on the state of balance of payments, the rate of inflation, domestic liquidity and employment (Iheanachor & Ozegbe, 2021). Thus, between 1986 and 2003, different exchange rate policies were experimented by the government in which no single exchange rate policy was allowed to make remarkable impact in the economy before replacing it with another policy. The inconsistency in policies coupled with lack of continuity in exchange rate policies further worsened the instability of the naira exchange rate (Aslam, 2016; Akinwunmi & Adekoya, 2016). The exact impact of a change in the policy rate is uncertain, because it depends again on the expectations on the interest rates and on domestic and foreign inflation. The relationship between exchange rate regimes and economic performance of the developing countries like Nigeria has gone beyond theories and principles but rather focus is on the reality of existing impact, for for instance the adoption of flexible exchange rate during the SAP era and the depreciating Naira exchange rate against key currencies are expected to affect Nigerian economic performance which has not been captured in existing literature thereby creating a knowledge gap. The paper is germane to assess the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The review of

related literature is contained in section two while the model is outlined in section three. In section four, the findings are presented which is followed by conclusion and recommendations in section five.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term exchange rate refers to the price of one country’s currency in relation to another country currency. It is the required amount of unit of a currency that can buy another currency. Accordingly to Maddison (1982) and Aliyu (2011), exchange rate fluctuations influence domestic prices through their effect on aggregate supply and demand. In general, when a country currency depreciates it will result in high import prices most especially if the country is an international price taker, while lower import prices result from appreciation. Adama, *et al.*, (2022) asserted that appreciation of exchange rate result in increasing imports and reduce exports while depreciation in exchange rate tend to cause a shift from foreign goods to domestic goods. Hence, it leads to diversion of income from importing countries to exporting countries through a shift in terms of trade. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (2019), exchange rate can be defined as the current market price for which one national currency can be exchange for another. It is normally expressed as the number of units of a domestic currency that will purchase one unit of a foreign currency or the number of units of a foreign currency that will purchase the unit of a domestic currency (Koirala, 2018).

On the other hand, economic growth has been defined in various ways in the literature. According to Omorokunwa and Ikponmwosa, (2014), it is seen as long-term change in an economy’s productive capacity. The productive capacity of the economy is the output that could be produced when all of the economy’s resources were fully and efficiently employed (Jhingan, 2005). Therefore, economic growth refers to an economy’s progress as a result of favorable circumstances, such as the progress made by the United Kingdom during the Industrial Revolution. In rich countries, increasing income levels is referred to as economic growth, while in impoverished countries it is referred to as economic development (Maddison, 1982). Economic growth is a positive change in the production of goods and services in an economy. It can also be referred to as increase in inflation-adjusted market value of goods and services produced by an economy over a period of time. It occurs when there is an increase in capital goods, labour force, technology, and human capital which is measured in terms of the increase in aggregated market value of additional goods and services produced, using estimates such as gross domestic product (Mankiw & Gregory, 1994; Ehigiator, *et al.*, 2020).

Theoretically, the relationship between exchange rate regime such as flexible exchange rate and economic performance has been a point of departure among scholars. For instance, the traditional school believes that volatility in exchange rate discourage trade while the portfolio theory argues that volatility in exchange rate creates risk such that risk seekers would trade in the mist of volatile exchange rate for profitability objective (Gbosi, 2005; Nwafor, 2017). This ambiguity has remained unresolved in the emerging economy like Nigeria that deserves investigation. Also, there is the purchasing power parity (PPP) which is perhaps one of the earliest and most popular theory of exchange rate. The theory posits that the exchange rate between two currencies would be equal to the relevant national price levels. It assumes the absence of trade barriers and transactions cost and existence of the purchasing power parity (Aslam, 2016). In this version, the PPP doctrine equates the equilibrium exchange rate of the ratio of domestic to foreign price level (Lawal, 2016).

$$\frac{E - Pd}{PE}$$

Where; E is the nominal exchange rate defined in terms of domestic currency per unit of foreign currency. Pd is the foreign price, PE level of perfect efficiency and absence of trade barriers, transaction cost and the purchasing power parity. This doctrine would be tantamount to the applications of the law of one price where all the countries produced explicitly the same tradable goods (Iwuoha & Awoke, 2019). It is important to know that the PPP is a major component of the monetary approach in which the PPP between any two currencies is the amount of the determination of equilibrium exchange rate. It is often

applied as a proxy for the monetary model in exchange rate analysis (CBN, 2019). The relevant version of PPP doctrine relates the equilibrium exchange rate to the product of the exchange rate in a base period and the ratio of the countries price indices (Argh, 1994). By definition, the PPP may be defined as (PPP) as:

$$\frac{E - Pd}{PE} RO$$

Where: Ro is the actual exchange rate at the base period (the number of units of domestic currency per unit of foreign currency). The PPP theory defines two equilibrium exchange rate systems. The first is the short run equilibrium exchange rate which is defined as the rate that exists under a pure freely floating exchange rate system. The other is the long-run equilibrium that would yield balance of payment equilibrium over a time period during cyclical fluctuations in the balance of payment (including those that relate to business cycle at home and abroad).

Similarly, the traditional flow model views exchange rate as the product of the interaction between the demand for and supply of foreign exchange (Lawal, 2016; Iheanachor & Ozegbe, 2021). In this model, the exchange rate is in equilibrium when supply equals demand for foreign exchange, (Barguelil, *et al.*, 2018). The exchange rate adjusts to balance the demand by the domestic resident for foreign exchange which depends on domestic resident's demand for domestic goods and assets. On the assumption that the foreign demand for domestic goods is determined essentially by domestic income, the relative income plays a major role to determine exchange rate under the flow model. Since assets demand can be seen as a demand on difference between domestic and foreign, interest rate differentials is other major determinants of the exchange rate in this frame work (Wood, *et al.*, 2004; Koirala, 2018).

In the same vein, the Solow growth model shows how growth in the labour force and advances in technology interact to affect output. The first step in building the model is to examine how the supply and demand for goods determines the accumulation of capital. To ensure this, labour force and technology are held fixed. The model enables us to describe the production distribution and allocation of the economy's output data. It shows how savings, population growth and technological process affect the growth of output over a given period of time (Unugbro, 2007).

From the empirical corridor, there are several studies in the literature that have attempted to evaluate the relationship between exchange rate fluctuation and economic growth in which mixed findings were uncovered. These authors employed several models such as ordinary least squares, error correction model, vector autoregressive model and autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) model. Onyekachi (2012) examined the impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria for a data period of 1980-2010. In addition to exchange rate, other explanatory variables included in the model were degree of openness, inflation rate and interest rate. The ordinary least square (OLS) methodology was employed for the study and findings indicated significant positive impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria in the period of study. Akpan and Atan (2012) appraised the relationship between changes in exchange rate and growth of real output in Nigeria using quarterly data for the period, 1986-2010. The study utilized two methods of analysis namely simultaneous equations approach and generalized method of moments (GMM) technique for the contemporaneous investigations between the variables. However, the study could not found evidence of strong direct relationship between exchange rate and output growth but rather economic growth is being affected directly by other monetary variables in Nigeria in the period of review. The study recommended improvement in exchange rate management which should encompass a broad program of economic reforms to complement the exchange rate policy in Nigeria.

Meanwhile, Isola, *et al.*, (2016) assessed the extent at which fluctuations in exchange rate had impacted on economic growth in Nigeria, 2003-2013. The study made real gross domestic product as a function of exchange rate, inflation rate, interest rate and broad money supply. Accordingly, none of the variables was found to be statistically significant in affecting economic growth in Nigeria. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was employed for the analysis. Iwuoha and Awoke (2019) appraised the extent at which real exchange rate affected non-oil export in Nigeria, 1975-2017. Using Johansen

cointegration and vector error correction model, the study found that long run relationship existed between non-oil exports, real exchange rate, trade openness and interest rate. Specifically, the study found that real exchange had significant negative impact on non-oil export while interest rate exerted significant positive relationship in Nigeria. The study recommended full deregulation of the exchange rates for the Nigerian economy. Morina, *et al.*, (2020) submitted that exchange rate is a key macroeconomic variable that affects international trade to the extent that real economy of each country is not left out. The paper assessed how exchange rate volatility affects economic growth of 14 Central and Eastern European countries covering data period of 2002-2018. Using panel data fixed effect regression technique, the study found evidence of significant negative effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in the selected European countries. The study recommended that policy makers may adopt different policy measures to ensure exchange rate stability.

Furthermore, Ehigiator, *et al.*, (2020) examined the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria, 1997-2017. The study made gross domestic product as the dependent variable while the explanatory variables included exchange rate, inflation rate and debt. The ordinary least square (OLS) method was employed for the study. Among other things, the study found a significant positive impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria. In their study, Abdu, *et al.*, (2021) investigated the impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria using data from 1986-2019. Utilizing the OLS methodology, the study found that exchange rate exerted significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria as against the significant negative influence of inflation rate and interest rate during the review period. The study recommended export promotion strategies and adequate security as a way of attracting foreign investors to Nigeria. Iheanachor and Ozegbe (2021) submitted that the Central Bank of Nigeria has been making concerted efforts over the last few decades aimed at stimulating the economy through sound monetary policy but with such efforts yielding little or no positive results. Their paper scrutinized the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria covering the period, 1986-2019. The ARDL model was employed for the study and findings indicated that exchange rate and two other explanatory variables namely inflation rate and foreign direct investments had significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommended the policy of export diversification mainly in the agriculture sector to increase output in Nigeria.

Similarly, Ewubare and Ushie (2022) in their paper seek to explore the extent at which exchange rate affected economic growth in Nigeria using data period, 1981-2020. In addition to exchange rate, interest rate and inflation rate were included in the model as explanatory variables. Using the ARDL model, the study found evidence of long run relationship between the variables. Specifically, the study also found that economic growth is significant and negatively responsive to changes in exchange rate and inflation rate contrary to its significant and positive response to changes in interest rate in Nigeria in the period under review. The study advocated a consistent exchange rate policy that will guarantee stability and realistic exchange rate. Ramoni-Perazzi and Romero (2022) employed a panel data spanning the period 1995-2019 using the GARCH methodology to explore the effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth for 194 countries. The control variables include trade openness, government spending, financial development, human capital development and investment. The estimation of both difference and system generalized method of moments were utilized by the study. Accordingly, the study found evidence of significant negative influence of exchange rate volatility on economic growth. An important observation is that the effect of volatility is lower in high-corrupt countries than low corrupt countries.

Meanwhile, Nwikina and Ekere (2024) appraised the effect of the exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1985–2021. The autoregressive distributed lag model was employed for the study and findings indicated that exchange rate had a long run relationship with economic growth. Specifically, the study found presence of weak negative correlation existing between exchange rate and GDP growth. Also, the study found that trade openness and foreign exchange reserves had significant positive effect on economic growth. However, the impact of interest rate on growth is negative and statistically significant. The study advocated that monetary policy should be effectively deployed to address issue of exchange rate stabilization. Adewale, *et al.*, (2024) examined to what extent exchange rates affect foreign direct investment in Nigeria covering the period 1981-2021. The explanatory variables, besides exchange rate,

include trade openness, interest rate, inflation rate and human capital development. The fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) regression technique was employed by the study. Accordingly, the study found that exchange rate had significant positive influence on FDI contrary to significant negative effect exerted by human capital development. However, the study could not find significant relationship between interest rate, inflation rate, trade openness and FDI in the period of review. Essentially, the study cautions against the continuous depreciation of the exchange rate so as not to deter foreign investors.

The Model

The research employed a simple linear regression technique similar to the models of Ewubare and Ushie (2022) and Adewale, *et al.*, (2024) using the ordinary least square (OLS) approach covering a data period of 2000-2024 and specified as follows:

$$GDP = f(EXC, INF, FRR) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

In log stochastic term, equation (1) can be estimated thus:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln EXC + \beta_2 \ln INF + \beta_3 \ln FRR + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

GDP= gross domestic product at 2010 constant price in billions of naira

EXC = nominal exchange rate (₦/\$)

INF = Inflation rate

FRR = foreign reserves in billions of naira

β_0 = constant while β_1 - β_3 coefficients to be estimated

Apriori Expectation: it is expected that exchange rate may affect economic growth positively or negatively while negative signs expected from inflation rate. Meanwhile, impact of foreign reserves on economic growth is expected to be positive.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Regression Results

Dependent Variable: LGDP

Method: Least Square

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics	Probability
Constant	5.91	10.76	0.00
EXC	0.50	6.29	0.00
INF	-0.13	-1.50	0.15
LFRR	0.26	4.98	0.00
$R^2 = 0.88, DW = 2.08, F\text{-Stat} = 42.4$			

Source: Extracted from Eview 12

Table 1 contains the results where the dependent variable is the real GDP used as proxy for economic growth while independent variables are exchange rate, inflation rate and foreign reserves. The results show that the independent variables account for 88% variation in economic growth as indicated by the fairly robust goodness of fit. Likewise, the F-statistic reveals that the model is statistically significant while the DW statistic suggests that serial correlation is not a problem in the model. Furthermore, the results suggest that in the absence of the three independent variables, economic growth will be positive. It can be observed from the results that exchange rate and foreign exchange reserve had significant positive impact on economic growth within the period of review. This further implies that a 1% increase in these

variables will increase in economic growth by 0.50% and 0.26% respectively. However, inflation rate exerted negative relationship with economic growth but statistically insignificant which implies that the negative impact is not felt by economic growth. These results is similar to the findings of Ehigiator, *et al.*, (2020), Iheanachor and Ozegbe (2021) and Nwikina and Ekere (2024) but contrary Abdu, *et al.*, (2021) and Adewale, *et al.*, (2024).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study examined the extent at which exchange rate affect economic growth in Nigeria with data covering 2000-2022. Two control variables were added to the model namely inflation rate and foreign reserves. Accordingly, the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth was investigated using OLS technique. Observably, it was discovered that effect of exchange rate and foreign reserves on economic growth is positive and statistically significant. Similarly, the effect of foreign reserves on economic growth is positive and statistically significant. However, inflation rate exerted negative but insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The findings of the study reinforces the importance of exchange rate in an economy as changes especially depreciation in the value of the local currency is deleterious on the economy. The is the situation in Nigeria where the consistence fall in the value of the naira has resulted in hyperinflation and the implication is high cost of living and severe economic hardship witnessed by the citizens. The exchange rate of the naira to the US dollar which stood at average of ₦500/US\$ in June 2023 had depreciated to over ₦1500/\$ in June 2024 making life unbearable for averages Nigerians. On the bases of the findings, the study recommended that policy makers may formulate effective exchange rate policy predicated on the strength of fiscal and monetary policies aimed at reducing misalignment in exchange rate for the naira. Secondly, strict foreign exchange control policies designed to reduce inflationary pressure should be the target of monetary policy makers. Finally, government may intensify efforts aimed at boosting productions thereby increasing output, exports and foreign reserves.

REFERENCES

- Adama, J.A., Ohwofasa, B.O., & Onabote, A.A, (2022). Empirical assessment of the impact of external reserves on economic growth in Nigeria. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 19(2), 295-305. doi:10.21511/imfi.19(2).2022.26.
- Adewale, A.M., Olopade, B.C., & Ogbaro, E.O. (2024). Effect of exchange rate on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *ABUAD Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 5(2), 302- 18. <https://doi.org/10.53982/ajsms.2024.0502.05-j>.
- Abdu, M., Umar, M.R., Mohammed, B., & Ajannah, J.M. (2021). Exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth nexus: An empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 5(2), 33-40.
- Adeniran, J.O., Yusuf, S.A., & Adeyemi, O.A., (2014). The impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the Nigerian economic growth: An empirical investigation. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(8), 224-234.
- Akinwunmi, A.A. & Adekoya, R.B., (2016). External reserves management and its effect on economic growth of Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Finance Management Research*, 4, 36-46.
- Akpan, E.O., & Atan, J.A., (2012). Effects of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 2(2), 01-14.
- Aliyu, S.U.R., (2011). Impact of oil price shock and exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *Research Journal of International Studies*, 3(4), 102-124.
- Aslam, A.L. (2016). Impact of exchange rate on economic growth in Srilanka. *World Scientific News*, 54: 252-266.
- Barguelil, A., Ben-Salha, O., & Zmami, M., (2018). Exchange rate volatility and economic growth. *Journal of Economic Integration*, 33(2), 1303-1336.

- Central Bank of Nigeria (2019). Statistical Bulletin. Available at: <https://www.cbn.gov.ng>.
- Ehigiator, H., Murtadho, A.M., Bhaumik, A., (2020). The relationship between the exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Human Science*, 4(4), 11-18.
- Ewubare, D.E., & Ushie, U.A., (2022). Exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth in Nigeria, 1981-2020. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 10(1), 41-55. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijdes.13>.
- Gbosi, A.N., (2005). Money, monetary policy and the economy. Port Harcourt, Sodek Publishing.
- Hicks, J.R., (1987). Keynes and the classics: A suggested interpretation. *Econometrica*, 5(2), 147-59.
- Iheanachor, N., & Ozegbe, A.E., (2021). The consequences of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigeria's economic performance: An autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach, *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences*. 10(2-3). 68-87. <https://doi.org/10.32327/IJMESS/10.2-3.2021.5>.
- IMF (2007)., *Balance of Payments Manual*: 5th Edition. International Monetary Fund.
- Isola, L.A., Atunde, I.O., Ahmed, V., & Abiola, A., (2016). Exchange rate fluctuation and the Nigeria economic growth. *Euro Economica*, 2(35), 127-142. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/11159/411>.
- Iwuoha, J.C., & Awoke, C.F., (2019). Impact of real exchange rate on non-oil exports in Nigeria. *DUTSE Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 8, 83-93.
- Jhingan, M.L., (2005). *International economics*. New Delhi, Vrinda Publications (P) Limited, 5th Edition.
- Koirala, S., (2018). An analysis of the impact of real effective exchange rate on economic growth of Nepal. *Parvaha Journal of Economic Management*, 12, 206-216.
- Lawal, E.O., (2016). Effect of exchange rate fluctuations on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 4(10), 32-39.
- Maddison, A., (1982). Growth and slowdown in advanced capitalist economies: Techniques of quantitative assessment. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 25(2), 649-698.
- Mankiw, N. G., & Gregory N. (1994). *Macroeconomics*. New York: Worth Publishers.
- Morina, F., Hysa, E., Ergün, U., Panait, M., & Voica, M.C. (2020). The effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth: Case of the CEE Countries. *Journal of Risk and Financial Managemet*, 13(177), 2-13. doi:10.3390/jrfm13080177.
- Nwafor, M.C., (2017). External reserves: Panacea for economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(33), 36-47.
- Nwikina, C., & Ekere, E. (2024). Impact of exchange rate on economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 12(3), 36-50). DOI: 10.37745/gjahss.2013/vol12n33650.
- Omorokunwa, O.G., & Ikponmwosa, N., (2014). Exchange rate volatility and foreign private investment in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Business Management*, 2, 146-154.
- Onyekachi, E.N., (2012). *The impact of exchange rate on the Nigeria economic growth, 1980-2010*. An unpublished B.Sc project submitted to the Department of Economics, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Caritas University, Amorji-Nike, Emene, Enugu State.
- Ramoni-Perazzi, J., & Romero, H. (2022). Exchange rate volatility, corruption, and economic growth. *Heliyon*, 8, e12328.
- Unugbro, A.O., (2007). The impact of exchange rate fluctuation on capital inflow: the Nigerian Experience 1980 – 2003. *The Nigerian Academic forum*, 13(2), 12 - 18.
- Wood, J., Wallace, J., Zeffane, R., Champan, J., Fromholtz, M., & Morrison, .V. (2004). *Organisational behaviour: A global perspective*. Australia: John Wiley and Sons, 3rd edition. 355-357